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IMPORTANT ECONOMIC DIRECTIONS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN THE SERVICE SECTOR

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Abstract - This article focuses on the development of small businesses and private entrepreneurship in the service sector. It shows that small businesses in the service sector in our country are investing very little in implementing innovations, and a number of specific features of these processes are analyzed, conclusions and suggestions are made.

Keywords- Service, Small Business, Innovation, Private Entrepreneurship, Innovative Activity, Service.

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of digital technologies in the world has become the "cornerstone" of technological innovation in all sectors of production. In this area, China, the USA and Japan are considered countries with advanced experience through their innovative development strategies, and according to the World Intellectual Property Organization, their share is 75% of the global number of granted

patents. In our country, in order to improve the innovative activities of industrial enterprises over the past five years, the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, which emphasizes "Widely introducing innovations into the economy, developing cooperative relations between industrial enterprises and scientific institutions", requires the development of service enterprises in our country, digitization of system activities, improvement of organizational and economic mechanisms, and further provision of innovative technologies, and this situation sets us a number of tasks to implement.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The following leading scientists who conducted their scientific research in this field in the world have expressed their scientific views.

According to the definition given by the French economist R. Cantillon, "an entrepreneur is a person who has the ability to foresee events and phenomena, takes all responsibility for himself, hopes to make a profit from his actions and is ready to lose at any cost."

Another economist, Y. Schumpeter (1883-1950), who conducted in-depth research in this area, stated that "an entrepreneur is an innovator, that is, a person who creates innovations." He also believes that "the task of an entrepreneur is to reform (renew) the method of production by implementing new discoveries." At the same time, he put forward the idea that the activities of an entrepreneur, viewing them in a broad sense, consist of using new technologies to produce new goods or modernize outdated ones based on a newly opened market or raw material base.

According to American economists K. McConnell and S. Brew, "an entrepreneur combines production factors in the process of producing goods and providing services and acts as a "catalyst".

According to economists of our republic Sh. Shodmonov and M. Rakhmatov, "...entrepreneurship differs from business in that entrepreneurship is an activity related to the production of products and the provision of services in the spirit of

creativity and innovation. Business is a broad concept in relation to it, and is generally an activity carried out from the point of view of making a profit”.

Uzbek scientists A.O‘lmasov and M.Sharifkhodjaev define “business in the broad sense as an activity aimed at earning income in a legal way... Entrepreneurship is an economic activity aimed at earning income by actually putting the material and monetary resources (capital) of people (property entities) into economic circulation. Entrepreneurship does not mean earning money at all, but rather earning income through creative activity.”

At the same time, one of the leading scientists of our Republic, S.S.Gulamov, admits that “entrepreneurial activity is manifested as a form of business and is carried out in its various spheres,” and at the same time, in his opinion, “an entrepreneur is an energetic person who has full or partial material or financial resources, and he uses these resources to organize his work (business).”

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This article uses comparative analysis and induction and deduction evaluation methods. Using the comparative method, statistical data were analyzed and scientific conclusions were drawn.

IV. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Indicators of innovative activity of small business entities in the service sector in our country, the implementation of technological, organizational, marketing innovations show a recent downward trend. According to studies conducted by the World Bank and the Center for Economic Research and Reforms, only 23.2% of firms in Uzbekistan have implemented product innovations and 14.4% have implemented technological innovations in the past 3 years. However, only 5% of these firms have spent more than \$ 100 on implementing innovation processes. This indicator is very low. Also, over the past three years, 10% of the entities participating in the surveys have applied advanced foreign experience, 13% of entities have implemented innovations using internal capabilities, and 7% of entities have used

outsourcing services for the implementation of innovations on a contractual basis. From these indicators, we can analyze that in our country, small businesses in the service sector are investing very little in implementing innovations. There are a number of specific features of this, and these are:

- low confidence in innovations;
- the presence of risks in the implementation of innovative activities;
- insufficient investments for innovations;
- lack of specialists in working with innovations.

In particular, in this regard, in the Samarkand region, the share of small businesses in the GRP in January-December 2023 was 72.8%. The largest number of newly established small enterprises and micro-firms was established in the trade sector - 3,254, in the industrial sector - 1,225, in agriculture, forestry and fisheries - 729, in accommodation and catering - 724, in the construction sector - 372, and in transportation and storage - 217.

Figure 1. Retail activity of small business entities providing services in Samarkand region (as of January 1, 2024)

By cities and districts, the largest volume of industrial production is accounted for by the city of Samarkand (3,702.6 billion soums), Urgut (1,760.0 billion soums), Jomboy (1,674.9 billion soums), Samarkand (1,380.4 billion soums), Toyloq (843.9 billion soums), and Bulungur (757.0 billion soums) districts. The volume of industrial production in Ishtikhan (242.8 billion soums) and Qoshrabot districts (138.4 billion soums) remains low. In January-December 2023, the share of small business entities in the gross regional product of the region amounted to 72.8 percent, compared to the same period in 2022 (70.4 percent). The highest shares of small businesses in the services sector correspond to Narpay district (share in total services (85.3%), Aqdaryo district (84.1%), Kattakurgan city (84.4%), Qoshrabot (84.3%) and Ishtikhon (84.0%) districts, while the lowest indicator corresponds to Samarkand city (48.8%) (Figure 2.3). The research analyzed the implementation of services by small business entities in the provision of services in the Samarkand region for the period 2020-2024, according to which, while in 2020 the share of small businesses in the provision of services was 68.9%, by 2024 this indicator had significantly decreased to 65.0%. This is due to the fact that in the total value of services in the Samarkand region, other than small business entities We can see that the share of sectors (for example, industry) has increased.

Figure 2. Activity of small business entities in the service sector in Samarkand region (2020-2024)

The impact of innovative development of small business entities in the service sector also requires the presence of components, which provide a great service for the further development of small business entities. At the same time, this structural unit can also serve as a source for the widespread introduction of innovative technologies into the activities of the sector (Figure 2.5).

Figure 3. Components of small business entities in the service sector according to their dependence on innovative development.

The development of small businesses in the service sector is one of the important economic directions. This sector serves to develop the services segment of the economy, increase employment and improve the well-being of the population.

V. CONCLUSION/RECOMMENDATIONS

In our opinion, the following actions are appropriate for this purpose. They are:

Firstly, in order to improve the legal and institutional conditions, it is necessary to reduce taxes and provide incentives for small businesses, simplify the licensing and permit procedures, and expand state programs supporting small entrepreneurship.

Secondly, in order to increase financial support and credit opportunities, it is necessary to reduce interest rates on bank loans, allocate grants and subsidies for small businesses, and attract private investments and venture capital.

Thirdly, further develop the service infrastructure, establish new trade and service outlets, improve transport and logistics services, and effectively use information and communication technologies.

Fourthly, in order to improve personnel training and education programs, it is necessary to organize training, seminars in the centers of service entities, increase their experience in foreign countries, and begin the supply of personnel based on the dual education system.

As a result of implementing these reforms, the number of small businesses in the service sector will increase, the volume and quality of services will increase, and new jobs will be created, which will have a positive impact on the country's economy.

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